

DECIDING ON GRAPE VARIETIES GRAPES TRAINING SYSTEMS AND METHODS

Nuraliyeva Farangiz Baxtiyor qizi

Gulistan state university

Group 25-20

+998 91-100 03-60

Xolmatov Islomjon G'ulom o'g'li

Gulistan state university

Master degree in Russian language

+998933247773

Islomxolmatov9@gmail.com

Abstract: Deciding on the grape variety is not an easy thing. It is crucial to consider the growing method we will choose, the varieties of grapes that thrive in our area and of course if we can market the product of our selected variety at a good price. There are two methods to start a vineyard: Growing autogenous plants or growing grafted cuttings. In any case, each variety has its own unique quality features, expressed under specific climate and soil requirements, such as pH or EC levels, water and nutrition requirements, temperature or sun exposure. Thus the selection and decision shall be careful and fact-based.

Key words: grape, variety, viniculture, plant, form, farming, vine, correction

Growing Autogenous Grapevines.

Since 1850-60, most European vine-growers periodically stopped the cultivation of autogenous vine plants. The reason was the appearance of a catastrophic enemy, which was unknown in Europe since then. The enemy is called Phylloxera (*Phylloxera vastatrix*) and is a soil aphid that is extremely harmful to vines. It is believed that the aphid came from America, due to the fact that American grapevines had already developed immunity, because of the long term symbiosis

with the pest. Before that, the main cultivars belonged to *Vitis vinifera* species, most of which are sensitive to the aphid. However, in areas that phylloxera problems have not appeared, some smallholder farmers still prefer to plant autogenous plants.

Growing Grafted Grapevine Cuttings.

As we mentioned above, during 1850, European producers started to seek for solution to defeat the phylloxera attack. The solution came from the same place as the attack, America. Native vine varieties of America have developed immunity against the aphid due to the long period of symbiotic relationship. Thus, they started to graft their traditional *Vitis vinifera* varieties on American rootstocks. Grafting is a commonly used technique by which we join together parts from two different plants so that they will grow together as a single plant. The upper part of the first plant is called scion and grows on the root system of the second plant, which is called rootstock. Eventually, we have a plant that combines all the advantages of its different components.

The preferred rootstocks, are numerous, depending mostly on their tolerance under certain soil and temperature conditions. Some of the most commonly used rootstocks belong to the following species:

Vitis riparia (e.g., Riparia Gloire de Montpellier)

Vitis rupestris (e.g., Rupestris du Lot)

A combination of Riparia-Rupestris

Rootstocks of the Berlandieri x Riparia group

Rootstocks of the Berlandieri x Rupestris group and many others

Each of the rootstocks varies significantly both in morphological characteristics and growing techniques.

Regardless of which method we are going to choose, we must be sure to buy our plants from a legitimate seller in order to avoid surprises.

Choosing Grape Variety

Grapevine Varieties

Due to the thousands of years of grape cultivation, thousands of varieties have been developed. Generally, we divide grape varieties into three major groups.

Winemaking varieties.

In this category, we have mostly European varieties, because of their long history in wine production. However, some American varieties are also important. Some commonly used winemaking varieties are: Cabernet Franc, Cabernet Sauvignon, Malbec, Merlot, Pinot Noir, Syrah, Concord (red varieties), Chardonnay, Pinot Blanc, Pinot Gris, Semillon, Gewurztraminer, Catawba, Delaware (white wines)

Currant producing varieties:

The most famous are Sultanina and Korinth

Table grapes varieties:

Cardinal, Perlette, Victoria, Ribier and others.

As we mentioned before, the grapevine is a climbing bush. This means that it needs a kind of supporting system in order to develop properly. Right after the installation of the vineyard, as soon as our plants have developed their first shoots, it is time to apply the shape our vines are going to have. For once again, selecting vine training pattern is a multifactorial decision. It depends on the climate conditions (winds, temperature, sun exposure), the type of soil, and the cultivated varieties. Training is achieved through support (stacking) and pruning. Through the right training, growers seek to achieve optimum plant development, conditions that prevent pests and diseases outbreaks (for example proper aeration and sunlight penetration) and facilitation of harvesting and other cultivation techniques. But even if those factors were ensured, in most cases we would still need staking, as a mature plant cannot support all the weight of mature grapes by itself.

There are several different vine shapes preferred for different cases. One way to classify training systems is based on the trunk height. Following this classification, we end up having two major training categories: Low trained and High trained

A.) Low trained category, includes vine shapes where we keep the trunk slightly sort 20-60cm (0,66 to 2 ft.).

B.) The high trained category includes vine shapes where we keep the trunk slightly high over 120cm or 3,9 ft.

The most common vine training systems are the following:

Goblet shape

This type of training is probably the oldest one. It is preferred in hot and dry areas where we have non-irrigated vineyards and poor soils.

Following this type of training, we often shape the trunk in 20-30 cm (0,66 to 1 ft.) height, keeping 3-8 cordons around the trunk so as to create a goblet. Goblet is a free shape technique, meaning it does not need any trellising.

Cordon shapes

Cordon system is often used in warm climates, like California.

Royal Cordon

This is a commonly used training technique by which farmers basically leave one main cordon per vine.

Two-sided Cordon

This training technique is similar to the royal cordon. The only difference is that there is a second cordon, bent opposite of the first one.

Guyot shape

This system is often used in cool climates. Farmers who choose this training technique, basically follow all the steps of two-sided training, with one main difference. They prune one cordon leaving 6-10 buds, and the second one leaving only two buds. The long cordon gives the fruiting canes, while the short one, will approximately produce two new cordons. Subsequently, one of these new cordons in pruned at 6-10 buds and the other at 2 buds. This way, producers continually replace the cordons.

Pergola

This training technique is often used to shape table grape varieties. However, it is not suggested for early harvested varieties. We find many variations of this technique globally. What is common in all cases is the tall trunk height and the horizontal layout.

Such a trunk height requires two years of effort where farmers keep pruning it. Once they have the optimum height, they install the wire plexus above the head, where they will train the vines.

Lyre or U shape

This shape is similar to the two-sided cordon, but here, the two main cordons are bent on two different trellis systems. Subsequently, each of these two cordons gives another pair of cordons which are now inclined on the two sides of the same wire just like at the two-sided cordon system. This training system offers a lot of advantages, including better aeration, better sunlight penetration, and grape shading. However, it requires more effort to install.

Used sources:

- 1. Users/007/Downloads/investitsii-v-selskoe-hozyaystvo.pdf**
- 2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/investitsii-v-selskoe-hozyaystvo/viewer>**
- 3. www.selxoz.ru**